

Brand Identity Guidelines

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DO NOT stretch the logo proportions.

DO NOT place the logo over confusing backgrounds.

DO NOT apply level properties like shadows.

DO NOT apply traces to the logo.

Color Palette

<p>#CB69D0 R203 G105 B208</p>			
<p>C35 M70 Y0 K0</p>			
<p>#55CDFF R85 G205 B255</p>			
<p>C60 M0 Y0 K0</p>			

A a

Sora

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNO
PQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmno
pqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

Light	<i>Light Italic</i>
Regular	<i>Italic</i>
Medium	<i>Medium Italic</i>
Bold	<i>Bold Italic</i>
ExtraBold	<i>ExtraBold Italic</i>

Whenever Sora is not an available option, please use **Arial** as a safe alternative.

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Contact us:

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The rules specified in this document are to be considered guidelines to better understand the project and to look at when designing something new, evolving its identity, or even when breaking the rules.

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